

Psychological Aspects of Teachers' Self-Development and Professional Self-Realization in Ukrainian Higher Education Through Coaching

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Abstract: This study investigates ways to improve the quality of higher education in Ukraine through coaching. The psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization of teachers through coaching were examined: motivation factors, emotional intelligence, reflection, and self-awareness were analyzed as integral components of coaching. Empirical research was conducted through semi-structured interviews with 37 participants. The study reviewed the most common coaching approaches (including traditional coaching using the GROW model, transformational, systemic, competence-based, generative, and existential coaching), identified three areas for implementing coaching in Ukraine's higher education system, and outlined five critical areas of requests (somatic-behavioral, emotional-volitional, mental-cognitive, socio-creative, and existential-spiritual spheres) related to the professional self-realization of university teachers in Ukraine. The results indicated the high effectiveness of coaching for personal self-development and professional self-realization of university teachers, suggesting that coaching indirectly impacts the overall quality of higher education. The correlation between coaching and talent management systems is traced, and the ADKAR model and specific coach culture cycles are recommended for implementing effective coaching in Ukrainian HEIs.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Koçluk
Mesleki kendini gerçekleştirme
Duygusal zekâ
Motivasyon
Yükseköğretim

Ukrayna Yükseköğretiminde Koçluk Yoluyla Öğretmenlerin Öz-Gelişim ve Mesleki Öz- Gerçekleşmesinin Psikolojik Boyutları

Özet: Bu çalışma, koçluk yoluyla Ukrayna'daki yükseköğretimin kalitesini artırmanın yollarını araştırmaktadır. Öğretmenlerin koçluk sürecindeki psikolojik öz-gelişim ve mesleki öz-gerçekleşme dinamikleri incelenmiş; motivasyon faktörleri, duygusal zekâ, yansıtma (refleksiyon) ve öz-farkındalık, koçluğun bütünlük bileşenleri olarak analiz edilmiştir. Yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler yoluyla 37 katılımcı ile gerçekleştirilen ampirik araştırmada, en yaygın koçluk yaklaşımları (GROW modeline dayalı geleneksel koçluk, dönüşümsel koçluk, sistemsel koçluk, yetkinlik temelli koçluk, üretici koçluk ve varoluşsal koçluk) incelenmiş, Ukrayna yükseköğretim sisteminde koçluğun uygulanabileceği üç temel alan belirlenmiş ve üniversite öğretmenlerinin mesleki öz-gerçekleşmesine yönelik beş kritik talep alanı (somatik-davranışsal, duygusal-iradevi, zihinsel-bilişsel, sosyo-yaratıcı ve varoluşsal-manevi boyutlar) ortaya konmuştur. Sonuçlar, koçluğun üniversite öğretmenlerinin kişisel öz-gelişimi ve mesleki öz-gerçekleşmesi üzerinde yüksek düzeyde etkili olduğunu ve dolaylı olarak yükseköğretimin genel kalitesini artırabileceğini göstermiştir. Ayrıca, koçluk ile yetenek yönetimi sistemleri arasındaki korelasyon izlenmiş ve Ukrayna yükseköğretim kurumlarında etkili bir koçluk kültürünün uygulanması için ADKAR modeli ile özel koçluk kültürü döngüleri önerilmiştir.

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1. Introduction

The psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization of teachers through coaching as a component of optimizing the higher education system face several challenges, one of which is the insufficient support for teachers in realizing their professional potential. The lack of a systematic approach to coaching support for the professional development of university educators can lead to stagnation of knowledge and skills within the teaching staff, professional burnout, and loss of life direction, which will negatively affect the quality of teaching and research. The constant psychological pressure from life circumstances, the demands for scientific achievements, and the overload of the educational process can also lead to the deterioration of teachers' physical and mental health. The ongoing Russian–Ukrainian war has exacerbated teachers' professional self-determination instability, as frequent shifts in educational policies and labor market demands undermine their internal motivation and capacity for strategic self-reflection (Bakhov et al., 2021). Neglecting these issues may lead to a decline in the quality of education and research in higher education, loss of personnel, demotivation of the teaching staff, and threats to the stability of educational processes. Therefore, exploring the prospects for implementing such modern and innovative approaches as coaching is critically essential for supporting the development of higher education in Ukraine.

A thorough analysis of methodological and conceptual issues of coaching from the perspective of psychological science can be found in the works of Palmer and Whybrow (2018) and Peláez Zuberbuhler et al. (2024). The authors of the first study provided a detailed description of perspectives and research in coaching psychology, offering a comparative analysis of coaching psychology approaches (behavioral and cognitive-behavioral, humanistic, constructive, systemic, existential, and being-focused) and identifying critical aspects of professional ethics in coaching psychology practice. Peláez Zuberbuhler et al. (2024) conducted a thorough meta-analysis of sizeable empirical data sets, which confirmed the effectiveness of coaching based on a positive psychological approach (positive psychological coaching) in working with individuals and organizations. However, these works did not provide data on applying such a coaching approach, specifically with employees of higher education institutions (HEIs) (2024).

The works of Kapoutzis et al. (2023) and Brock (2008) present extensive studies of coaching as a cultural, social, and historical phenomenon. The study of behavioral and cognitive models of organizations that developed a coaching culture, presented in peer-reviewed scientific articles published between 2014 and 2022, allowed Kapoutzis et al. (2023) to conclude that coaching culture creates conditions for leadership, improves the psychological climate, and enhances mutual understanding and self-realization of employees and managers. The well-known researcher of the history of coaching, Brock (2008), analyzed the social prerequisites for the emergence and stages of coaching development, identifying key events that influenced its establishment as a profession. In her subsequent research, he notes that in the future, coaching should evolve into a dominant worldview and a global culture of humanity, becoming a leading style of interaction between people in various contexts, including educational ones (Brock, 2008).

Studying the scientific foundations of coaching in the education system (academic coaching, coaching in education, pedagogical coaching, educational coaching) is an essential direction of modern psychological science. Among more than 100,000 peer-reviewed scientometric articles devoted to the empirical study of coaching in education published in 2023–2024, it is worth noting the works of Ries et al. (2024), Packard et al. (2024), and van der Baan et al. (van der Baan et al. (2024)). For example, the research by Ries et al. (2024) demonstrated how the collaboration of seven university-based teacher preparation programs contributed to implementing coaching for equity in educational institutions, while Packard et al. (2024) traced how mentoring

ecosystems are formed on university campuses through coaching, while van der Baan et al. (2024) studied how career coaching in higher education helps students in further professional self-realization. These and numerous other studies indicate the importance of implementing coaching to optimize education, academic growth, and personal support for students and university teachers. However, in Ukraine, such research is still scarce. In particular, the issue of using coaching in Ukraine's higher education system has been addressed in the works of Chaika (2021) and Hurkova et al. (2022). Studying management styles in Ukrainian HEIs during the global COVID-19 pandemic, Chaika (2021) suggests transitioning from "crisis management" to coaching educational culture and leadership. Hurkova et al. (2022) studied and substantiated the importance of coaching in preparing educational workers in Ukraine.

The works above revealed essential aspects of the theory and practice of coaching in education; however, the issue of implementing coaching approaches in Ukraine's higher education system has not been sufficiently studied. The impact of coaching culture and philosophy on organizations providing educational services, the development of coaching as a profession, and mentoring systems in educational institutions also require further study, considering the specificities of Ukraine's education system. Meanwhile, the lack of a coaching culture within an academic faculty is one of the crucial factors contributing to the insufficient effective self-development and professional realization of teachers in Ukrainian higher education. Often, a combination of the authoritarian management style with the "common sense" management creates a toxic environment inhibiting continuous self-development, initiative, and agility.

In this context, this study aimed to explore the prospects for improving Ukraine's higher education system by identifying the psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization of university teachers through coaching. The tasks included a theoretical study of the psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization of teachers in the higher education system, an analysis of the effectiveness of coaching programs to support professional and personal growth, the study of the impact of motivational factors, emotional intelligence, reflection, and self-awareness on the process of self-development and professional self-realization of teachers, identifying problems and challenges faced by teachers, and developing recommendations for improving the system of support for university faculty through coaching in HEIs in Ukraine. Overall, the study outlines the potential and prospects of introducing or improving coaching programs for teachers in Ukrainian higher education.

2. Literature Review

The problem of forming the university's corporate culture has increasingly attracted scientists' attention in recent years. It is recognized that modern corporate culture is an integral characteristic of any organization and one of the key notions in organizations' innovative development and strategic management (Makaryan, 2023). Identification of teachers with the university, as with the organization of a special type, implies that they recognize its ideals, strictly adhere to the generally accepted rules and norms of behavior, and internally accept the corporate values common to the organization. Only in this case will the university's cultural values become teachers' values, occupying a place in the motivational structure of their behavior (Tahiraj & Krek, 2022).

Many authors emphasize that coaching can be particularly beneficial in the higher education sector, where it can be adopted in various domains. This is done by supporting 'the development of students, teachers, school leaders and the educational institutions of which they are part' (Thomson, 2018) to achieve their targets and helping them discover any hidden potential or goals. However, it must be acknowledged that coaching is a new field with ongoing

debate on its success in HEIs (Stan-Missouri, 2024, July 31). Although limited research exists concerning how effective coaching is in HEIs, some research has shown positive outcomes from using this method (Newell, 2024, October 16). Some authors have studied the effectiveness of coaching support in teacher training through experimental trials (Cohen et al., 2024). The research results proved that using coaching is a reliable means of improving the effectiveness of university teacher preparation, accelerating skill development, and contributing to their further professional self-realization. In their work, Capstick et al. (2019) demonstrated that full-time and part-time students who participated in the “Academic Coaching for Excellence” (ACE) program for academically at-risk students had significant GPA increases compared to students who did not participate in the program. Analyzing coaching practices in higher education, Hunaiti (2021) also obtained results that indicate the effectiveness of coaching in improving the quality of education for Generation Z students, increasing awareness of research project management, transforming educational organizations from “organizations for learning” into “learning organizations,” and more.

In the works of Garvey and Stokes (2022), more important issues of the theory and practice of coaching and mentoring were resolved. The authors thoroughly analyzed the impact of the global COVID-19 pandemic on the use of coaching in various fields. They made a large-scale comparative analysis of coaching practices in different countries: the USA, Australia, Czech Republic, Saudi Arabia, Hong Kong, Sri Lanka, and African and North American countries. Some authors (Kamarudin et al., 2020) outlined the theoretical principles of applying three models: zone of proximal development (ZPD), Biggs’s presage-process-product model, and GROW in various coaching and mentoring contexts. Wefald et al. (2021), using the example of the one-year “Snyder Leadership Legacy Fellows” program for students at Kansas State University, studied how leadership coaches helped them overcome the challenges of professional self-realization. Diller et al. (2021) found that coaching effectively meets university students’ autonomy needs. Ukrainian researcher Dzikovska (2019) demonstrated that coaching as an innovative pedagogical technology ensures high-quality training and develops leadership qualities in university students.

In the article by Vlachopoulos (2021), the issue of organizational change management in higher education in the United Kingdom (UK) through executive coaches and leadership coaching was explored. The research showed that academic leaders and university administrators improved their strategic planning and decision-making skills by working with coaches. They developed critical soft skills: responsibility, honesty, creativity, resiliency, empathy, and proactivity. Hakro and Mathew (2020), using case studies in HEIs in the Middle East, also demonstrated the value and effectiveness of coaching in working with academic leaders, administrators, and university faculty. Their research results confirmed that coaching promotes personal development and professional self-realization. Studies by Robinson (2015) and Warren (2019) also focused on academic coaching in higher education. In particular, Robinson (2015) conducted a survey that led to an understanding of academic coaching and identified the functional responsibilities of coaches in education. A definition of coaching psychology and its implementation in practice was carried out by Passmore and Lai (2020); this allowed the authors to find that research work has significantly contributed to the improvement of practical techniques, in particular through the introduction of empirically based approaches and techniques that improve the effectiveness of coaching sessions. Richter et al. (2021) conducted a systematic review and classification of tools and techniques, finding that positive psychological coaching uses many techniques, including positive thinking, goal setting, reflection, resilience development, and motivational interviewing. Ukrainian researchers Zelenin et al. (2023) identified the most effective

coaching methods in education as case studies, discussions, emotional stimulation, mosaic, and project-based methods.

Methods for improving students' coaching practice are disclosed in the work of Iordanou et al. (2016). Leach and Green (2016) explored ways to optimize the educational experience through coaching and positive psychology. In the study by Pechac and Slantcheva-Durst (2021), a link was found between coaching and the required number of credit hours to complete a course. Grant and Atad (2021) revealed the impact of coaching and positive psychology on various aspects of well-being and goal-focused self-regulation of MBA students. Atkinson et al. (2022), viewing coaching as an educational philosophy aimed at supporting learners' personal development and professional growth to maximize their potential, considered high-quality coaching feedback an essential educational tool. Gannon et al. (2022) studied how coaching can be used to develop leadership qualities in senior leaders in HEIs, and the empirical data from the dissertation research by Martinez (2015) demonstrated the effectiveness of academic coaching in improving students' academic engagement and performance. Grant (2020) proposed an evidence-based framework for applying coaching in educational practice – the integrated model of goal-focused coaching. In his book, van Nieuwerburgh (2012) thoroughly analyzed the prospects for implementing coaching in the educational environment, explored the role of coaching for educational leaders and the possibilities of coaching for teachers and parents, and outlined ways to create a coaching culture for learning. Meanwhile, Erchul (2023) confirmed the importance of integrating educational coaching and counseling to support effective teaching practices and enhance teachers' professional competence. The study by Burleigh et al. (2023) also confirmed the impact of coaching on improving pedagogical effectiveness in higher education.

In many respects, colleges now exemplify corporate strategic thinking and financial planning. These reforms are part of a forceful neoliberal approach that has revolutionized the public sector; the changes in higher education mirror those that have reshaped the country's health care system, tax collecting, policing, and education in general. Universities, vying for students now as their primary source of income and contending for a place in various league tables, have progressively acted more like profit-seeking corporations than altruistic institutions. As a result, academics are under increased pressure to teach well, publish research articles, submit funding applications, stay current on digital teaching and learning innovations, and participate in information sharing. Coaching also plays an important role. However, practical implementations of these paradigm shift changes have not yet been investigated. In Ukraine, this gap is especially evident, considering the blistering transformations that the national higher education system has had to undergo since the country gained independence.

3. Material and Method

This theoretical study closely examined the impact of coaching on the self-development and professional self-realization of university teachers. It reviewed scientific literature and previous studies related to the psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization of teachers, coaching in higher education, and leadership, along with a content analysis of open sources highlighting the practice of applying coaching in Ukrainian higher education. The research employs a qualitative approach and is based on a constructivist paradigm. It assumes that reality is subjective and socially constructed by individuals based on their experiences and social interactions. Moreover, according to the constructivist concept, learning does not just occur through the conventional lecture approach as teachers stand before the class. However, constructivists believe that learning happens when a student gains

information via doing and experimenting. Thus, this philosophical research paradigm correlates with the coaching paradigm.

The first stage of the study involved examining the most common coaching approaches in higher education: traditional coaching using the GROW model (goals, reality, options, will), transformational, systemic, competence-based, generative, and existential coaching. The basis for constructing an array of coaching approaches for examination is determined by the view of integrating a coaching culture as a pivotal aspect of organizational development. It is assumed that this cultural shift moves organizations from traditional management styles to more collaborative, reflective, and growth-oriented ones. Understanding the developmental stages of a coaching culture is essential for organizations aiming to harness its full potential. This allowed for revealing the essence and specifics of each approach and identifying their strengths and weaknesses. In the second stage, using content analysis of open sources, as well as observation methods and semi-structured interviews with teachers ($n = 37$) from Ukrainian HEIs, three directions for implementing coaching in the Ukrainian higher education system and five key areas of coaching requests among teachers of Ukrainian HEIs were identified. The sample size was determined by the authors' ability to process the results of semi-structured interviews and by avoiding the scattering of codes and categories during processing. Potential biases in participant selection could be caused by generational differences – in particular, young teachers of Generation Y could perceive organizational innovations, such as coaching, more positively than representatives of Generation X and Baby Boomers. The sampling method implied random selection from the list of teaching staff in participating HEIs. Based on the approaches reviewed in the first stage of the study and the data obtained in the second stage, a coaching support model was developed, aimed at adapting coaching to the needs of university teachers, considering workload, professional, scientific, and leadership development needs, as well as psychological, cultural, and social aspects.

The study of motivational factors affecting teachers' self-development and professional self-realization indicated the presence of different types of motivation: intrinsic, extrinsic, social, cognitive, autonomous, and emotional. Using the deduction method, it was established that coaching can contribute to developing each type of motivation and help establish personal motivation for achieving professional and personal goals. It was found that coaching provides teachers with tools for better awareness of their internal motives, increases external incentives by defining clear goals and ways to achieve them, creates a supportive social environment, stimulates cognitive interest, and ensures autonomy in decision-making. This, in turn, contributes to the overall increase in teaching effectiveness, personal growth, and professional self-realization. The next step of the study focused on investigating the systemic connection between emotional intelligence, reflection, and self-awareness in the process of self-development and professional self-realization of university teachers. It analyzed how these psychological components collectively influence the effectiveness of coaching programs. The information reviewed allowed for establishing that the development of emotional intelligence contributes to a better understanding of one's own emotions and those of others enhances communication effectiveness, and creates a favorable learning environment. Reflection enables teachers to analyze their experiences and find ways to improve them. At the same time, self-awareness helps to identify personal strengths and weaknesses, set realistic goals, and formulate strategies to achieve them. This allowed for identifying coaching methods that can significantly contribute to developing these components, including individual sessions, group discussions, exercises for awareness and reflection, and more.

Based on the collected information, the synthesis method was used to identify factors that contribute to the professional self-realization of teachers. It was found that these factors

include motivation, the development of professional skills, a supportive environment, access to resources for continuous learning, opportunities for creative fulfillment, recognition and evaluation of teachers' achievements, and coaching and mentoring. Since these factors enable teachers to feel more confident in their abilities, stimulate their further professional growth, and increase job satisfaction, it was established that integrating these factors into coaching programs helps create favorable conditions for the professional self-realization of teachers. The final stage of the study was devoted to developing coaching types and directions relevant to Ukrainian HEIs. The specifics of the national education system, cultural and social contexts, and teachers' professional needs were considered.

4. Results

The results of semi-structured interviews were processed using the standard toolkit of grounded theory, that is, open coding and categorization. The following categories were formulated: teaching excellence, communication skills, leadership development, teamwork efficiency, solving academic and personal problems, self-realization, and career progression. The obtained results correlate with the content analysis results, which testifies to successful triangulation and, thus, constitutes evidence of validity and reliability. One of the most common coaching approaches in higher education is the classical GROW model (goals, reality, options, will). This model focuses on clearly defining goals, analyzing the current situation, considering possible courses of action, and planning specific steps to achieve desired results. It helps teachers structure their thoughts and actions, concentrating on achieving specific goals. Transformational coaching is another widely used modern approach focusing on achieving profound internal changes by overcoming internal fears, prejudices, and limitations. It helps university teachers recognize their misinterpretations of reality, correctly identify their life priorities and values, and transform obstacles into opportunities for personal growth and professional self-realization.

System coaching fosters the development of a comprehensive vision of oneself as an element of a unified educational system, which includes interaction with students, colleagues, and university administration, as well as an understanding of sociocultural contexts and processes of societal change. This coaching approach is methodologically pluralistic, as it integrates methods of group dynamics, psychodrama, and client-centered, narrative, and systemic approaches. System coaching helps university teachers better understand their work tasks, roles, and functions. It also improves their ability to effectively interact with various system elements to resolve complex professional situations and conflicts. This coaching approach stimulates the development of leadership qualities and personal effectiveness and positively influences the awareness of professional career prospects and self-realization.

Competency-based coaching is an approach that focuses on developing specific knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for university teachers' professional activities. This coaching approach helps identify the teacher's strengths and weaknesses, develop a program for improving competencies, and determine criteria for progress toward achieving set goals. This approach can be recommended for university teachers ready to enhance their competence in specific areas of knowledge for professional self-realization. In turn, generative coaching, which is a synthesis of Ericksonian hypnosis models, generative trance, third-generation neuro-linguistic programming, emotional intelligence development technologies, and practices from Buddhism and Aikido, helps generate new ideas and solutions by interacting with the unconscious. This type of coaching fosters deep learning, changes in thinking strategies, and personal and professional growth. Generative coaching can help university teachers overcome

crises, resolve internal conflicts, and re-evaluate themselves and their life situations to develop and implement ambitious projects and innovative approaches in the educational process.

Additionally, there is existential coaching. This coaching approach focuses on finding meaning and value in university teachers' professional activities. It helps university teachers better understand their professional identity, comprehend the meaning of their lives, goals, and mission, and live and work in a way that aligns with their essence, energizes them, and enhances motivation and satisfaction from professional self-realization. Each coaching approach discussed has unique features and advantages that can be effectively applied to promote the self-development and professional self-realization of teachers in the higher education system. The choice of a specific approach or a combination of approaches depends on the teachers' individual needs and requests and the specific context in which they work. Implementing coaching according to the needs of university teachers is an important step in ensuring its effectiveness and achieving the desired results. In higher education, coaching is primarily aimed at developing all participants in the educational process—diagnosing the latent potential of students, graduate students, teachers, and university administration to maximize its realization. In this way, higher education coaching optimizes teaching and scientific-pedagogical activities without replacing them. Applying various coaching approaches in higher education also involves combining coaching and self-coaching, which promotes the self-development and professional self-realization of teachers, students, and leaders in the higher education system.

Content analysis of open sources highlighting the practice of implementing coaching in Ukraine's higher education system demonstrated the presence of three main directions. Firstly, coaching is taught as an academic discipline. Coaching courses have become part of the educational programs at institutions such as Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Mykhailo Dragomanov State University of Ukraine, Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Odesa Polytechnic National University, Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Cherkasy State Technological University, Petro Mohyla Black Sea National University (Mykolaiv), National Technical University "Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute," and many other leading universities in Ukraine. Secondly, scientific research was conducted by university lecturers. These studies cover not only coaching requests in education but also issues of management activities, professional and personal development of staff, efficiency improvement, optimization of decision-making processes, career development, leadership, personal self-development, tutoring, mentoring, and self-realization in various professions. Thirdly, university lecturers in Ukraine apply the coaching paradigm—philosophy, culture, methodology, methods, and coaching technologies to optimize the educational process: teaching, upbringing, personality development, and competency formation for their subsequent application in personal and professional self-realization.

Observations and semi-structured interviews allowed us to identify five key areas of requests related to self-development and professional self-realization of university lecturers in Ukraine ($n = 37$), which they most often bring to coaches or engage in self-coaching. In the Somatic-behavioral sphere, these requests help university lecturers find new, more productive action algorithms (habits) and address psychophysiological issues, such as accelerating recovery and overcoming stress in unregulated workloads and intensified work. These issues have been particularly exacerbated by the challenges of the global COVID-19 pandemic and later by the Russian–Ukrainian war. The emotional-volitional sphere involves questions about how to, on the one hand, infuse the educational space with psychological support and constructive emotions during interactions with colleagues and students and, on the other hand, how to learn volitional self-regulation and develop emotional intelligence to achieve current goals in self-

development and self-realization in personal and professional life. In the Mental-cognitive sphere, educators' requests to coaches in this area aim to develop competencies for deeper analysis of academic content, the ability to plan, effectively manage time, think strategically, set scientific and creative goals and achieve them, implement innovative technologies, give and receive constructive feedback from colleagues, and plan schedules for their professional and academic development and self-realization. In the social-creative sphere, systemic interaction in HEIs educational environment involves professional socialization, the self-actualization of creative potential, and the development of leadership qualities for self-realization in various social and cultural contexts. The modern university lecturer must respect cultural differences within the team, as understanding and considering social and cultural diversity helps create an inclusive educational environment where everyone feels valued. In the existential-spiritual sphere, these requests relate to the university lecturer's reflection on their life scenarios and perspectives, including which direction to steer their professional career, what meaning to find in pedagogical activities, who, where, when, and how to improve their professional skills and qualifications, how to perceive spiritual challenges, and other questions determining university lecturers' professional self-realization. This is described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Fields of requests for coaching in higher education. Author's own design.

Each specific coaching request area for higher education teachers involves applying appropriate tools from one or more approaches. For example, addressing goal-setting requests from the mental-cognitive sphere would be appropriately handled using the classical GROW model, while coaching requests from the existential-spiritual sphere would require a combination of transformational, systemic, generative, and existential coaching approaches and techniques. Thus, the qualifications of a coach providing coaching support for university teachers in Ukraine should include training, knowledge, skills, and experience in applying various coaching approaches, methods, techniques, and tools. An analysis of the content of coaching requests for teachers in Ukraine's higher education system indicates that coaching in this context should align with teachers' specific professional activities and consider their unique challenges and needs. These challenges and needs can be structured into a coaching support model for university teachers (see Figure 2).

Motivational factors are vital in teachers' self-development and professional self-realization through coaching. Understanding these factors helps properly structure coaching sessions to ensure maximum effectiveness and achieve desired results (see Figure 3). Coaching can significantly enhance intrinsic motivation, helping teachers discover internal sources of inspiration and identify

personal goals and values that drive them toward self-improvement. It can also assist teachers in identifying external motivational factors that stimulate them and developing strategies to achieve these. Coaching fosters social motivation by helping teachers establish effective relationships, share experiences, and collaborate with others. Coaching supports cognitive motivation and allows teachers to create individualized learning plans, access professional development resources, and pursue continuous learning. It also promotes autonomous motivation by allowing teachers to independently set their goals, choose strategies to achieve them and take responsibility for their actions. Additionally, coaching helps teachers develop positive emotions, such as satisfaction from achievements and joy from successful interactions with students and colleagues, which enhances their motivation for self-improvement.

Motivational factors are complex and multifaceted, and their impact on self-development and professional self-realization through coaching varies depending on university teachers' individual needs and circumstances. Coaching that considers various motivational factors can significantly increase the effectiveness of self-development, fostering personal growth and professional self-realization of teachers in higher education. The development of emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to be aware of and regulate one's own emotions and the emotions of others, which also plays a vital role in the process of self-development and professional self-realization of university teachers. University teachers develop personal and social skills through coaching methods and techniques. On a personal level, they cultivate self-awareness, which involves recognizing their own emotions, understanding their causes, assessing their consequences, and self-regulation—the ability to adapt and shift into productive emotional states. Socially, they enhance their social awareness, including empathy and the capacity to perceive others' emotions, along with relationship management skills such as inspiring others, resolving conflicts, facilitating change, and strengthening interpersonal connections. These competencies enable them to foster a more supportive and effective learning environment.

Figure 2. Model of coaching support for higher education teachers. Author's own design.

This creates an educational environment characterized by effective collaboration and mutual understanding, low conflict, positive relationships, an excellent psychological climate, and an understanding of the emotional needs of all participants in the educational process (students, teachers, administration)—all of which contribute to the development and professional self-realization of both teachers and students.

Figure 3. Motivational factors of self-development and professional self-realization of university teachers through coaching. Author's own design.

Reflection and self-awareness are also essential components of coaching for higher education teachers, contributing to enhancing their professional competencies in teaching practice. These components help university teachers better understand themselves, their actions, and their consequences, analyze the reasons for their successes and failures, and identify their strengths and weaknesses. In coaching sessions, university teachers' reflection becomes a prerequisite for recognizing behavioral and thinking patterns when interacting with colleagues and students, which determines professional achievements and prospects for self-improvement and shapes individual plans for professional self-realization. In turn, self-awareness, the understanding of one's motives, emotions, and thoughts, is also a crucial component of coaching for university teachers. Developing self-awareness through coaching enables teachers to understand better how their emotions and thoughts influence educational processes: teaching, communication with colleagues, scientific activities, and professional self-realization. Productive coaching methods for self-awareness among university teachers may include self-observation, self-assessment, case analysis, and feedback from the coach and oneself.

Reflection and self-awareness provide a foundation for teachers' more profound understanding of themselves and their professional activities. This allows for identifying internal and external obstacles and developing effective strategies to overcome them. For example, a teacher who recognizes that the fear of making mistakes prevents them from experimenting with innovative teaching methods can, through coaching, develop a plan of action to overcome this fear and increase their confidence. Reflection and self-awareness contribute to the development of emotional intelligence, which is essential for effective teaching and interaction with students. University teachers who recognize and analyze their emotions manage stress better, prevent professional burnout, maintain a positive emotional state, and create a favorable educational environment. The factors considered below

collectively create conditions for the self-realization of teachers in higher education, allowing them to achieve the maximum actualization and realization of their potential both in professional and personal spheres (Table 1).

Table 1.
Factors contributing to the professional self-realization of university teachers

Factor	Overview
Motivation and personal goals	Motivational factors such as personal goals, values, and interests are essential for teachers' professional self-realization. They encourage teachers to seek new opportunities to develop and improve their skills.
Professional development	Teachers' self-realization is often linked to their professional growth, which includes advanced training, participation in research projects, publication of scientific articles, defense of dissertations, and improvement of teaching methods.
Social support	Support from colleagues, students, and administration is vital. Positive interpersonal relationships and support promote professional self-realization, self-esteem, and self-confidence.
Recognition and value	Teachers experience professional fulfillment when their work is recognized and valued (e.g., through awards, promotion to positions of greater responsibility, and public recognition of their achievements).
Development of personal qualities	Professional self-realization is associated with developing personal qualities such as emotional intelligence, leadership skills, adaptability to change, and creativity.
Participation in professional unions and networks	University teachers are usually actively involved in professional unions and networks, facilitating the exchange of experience, new ideas, and development.
Self-development through coaching and mentoring	Coaching, self-coaching, and mentoring are practical tools for teachers' self-development. They help the entity's personal and professional goals, develop strategies for achieving them, and support their professional fulfillment.

Source: Compiled by the author

Coaching has a significant impact on the professional self-realization of university teachers, enriching this process with several key elements: it stimulates teachers' self-awareness, helping them better understand their strengths and weaknesses, as well as personal goals and motivations; it promotes the development of strategies for achieving goals; it provides systematic feedback that helps teachers evaluate their progress and make necessary adjustments to their actions and strategies. Moreover, coaching develops teachers' self-regulation skills and adaptability to change, which is crucial for successful professional self-realization. It helps them better respond to challenges and changes in the professional environment, developing constructive management strategies. Coaching employs various methods, technologies, and tools to develop the professional competence of teachers in higher education. These tools include active listening, deep questioning, a trusting environment, encouragement and motivation, goal-setting, strategy development, reflection and self-analysis, high-quality feedback, and more. These tools contribute to developing teachers' professional skills, enhancing the effectiveness of their activities, and fostering personal growth.

Implementing coaching programs in higher education encompasses challenges and opportunities that must be considered. Among the existing challenges, the most significant are aligning participants' expectations with actual outcomes and creating a supportive environment for program participants. One opportunity is the potential to improve the quality of teaching and learning in universities by developing teachers' professional skills through coaching to enhance students' academic performance and increase their satisfaction with the learning process. Another opportunity is the potential to increase motivation and job satisfaction

among teachers. Feeling supported and acquiring personal and professional development opportunities can stimulate their work effectiveness. Additionally, a significant opportunity is the potential to create a culture of openness and form an environment of maximum self-realization for all participants in the educational process at universities. Coaching programs can build trustful relationships between teachers and administration and create an environment where tolerance for change and continuous self-development is considered the norm. Coaching types and directions relevant to the Ukrainian higher education system are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Types and directions of coaching recommended for use in the practice of Ukrainian HEIs

Type or direction of coaching	Overview
Culturally sensitive coaching	Given the specifics and history of Ukrainian culture, viewing all participants' traditions, values, and characteristics in the educational environment is essential. A culturally sensitive approach will help coaches better understand the psychological characteristics of program participants and create strategies that inclusively consider their needs.
Integrated approach to professional development	Considering the various aspects of professional activity, coaching can offer an integrated approach to competence development, including academic and interpersonal aspects.
Coaching on the effective use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT)	University teachers' use of videoconferencing and online platforms and mastery of information and communication technologies (ICT) can facilitate the accessibility and speed of coaching and educational services, especially in remote regions of Ukraine and abroad. This can reduce traveling time and increase the overall efficiency of learning.
Coaching for postgraduate students and young researchers	In Ukraine, the young scientific community is of particular interest. Coaching can help them develop scientific and pedagogical skills, promoting personal growth and professional fulfillment.
Coaching for communities of practice	Establishing and coaching communities that bring together teachers and researchers to share experiences can effectively support and develop the teaching corps in Ukrainian higher education.
Coaching program for students in higher education	Coaching can be used in training courses and to support students in solving academic and personal problems, contributing to their academic success and further careers.

Source: Compiled by the author

The potential application of these types and directions of coaching in the Ukrainian higher education system could significantly impact the development of education quality, the enhancement of motivation among faculty and students, and the overall success and competitiveness of Ukrainian universities on the international level.

3. Discussion

The study aimed to explore the psychological aspects of using coaching for the self-development and self-realization of university faculty members. The results have led to practical recommendations for introducing coaching philosophy, culture, various coaching approaches, methods, and tools into the Ukrainian higher education system. These recommendations are mainly based on a meta-analysis of sources on the topic of "coaching culture" presented in the work of Gormley and van Nieuwerburgh (2014), which demonstrates how coaching culture impacts the effectiveness of educational institutions, and on the study by Bradley et al. (2024), which shows that training in coaching and coaching culture strengthens self-efficacy and contributes to better GPA outcomes for students, as well as improving the basic skills of university faculty members.

The psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization of university faculty through coaching, as revealed in this study, emphasize the importance of considering motivational factors, emotional intelligence, reflection, and self-awareness to enhance the effectiveness of coaching programs. It was found that developing these components contributes to increased job satisfaction. Additionally, it was established that coaching enhances professional competence, reduces stress, improves emotional intelligence, and develops leadership skills. The results indicate that coaching not only promotes personal growth and professional realization of university faculty members but also serves as a factor in optimizing the quality of higher education overall. Among other factors contributing to the professional self-realization of university faculty are motivation and personal goals, professional development, social support, recognition and value, the development of personal qualities, participation in professional unions, self-development through mentoring, coaching, and self-coaching, which should be highlighted.

Identifying the critical needs and requests for coaching among faculty in Ukrainian higher education institutions made it possible to structure a coaching support model for university faculty that included professional and academic self-development, psychological support, leadership development, readiness to handle teaching loads, and work by the administrative requirements of the university's organizational structure, as well as considering the cultural and social contexts that have gained significant importance in the context of the crises in Ukrainian education and society as a whole since 2020. Thus, among the various types and directions of coaching recommended for use in Ukrainian universities, the culturally sensitive coaching approach became especially relevant in the context of the social challenges posed by the global COVID-19 pandemic. In the study by Vovk and Ponomarenko (2023), some strategies for overcoming psychological barriers faced by university faculty in Ukraine at the beginning of 2020 due to the mass transition of Ukrainian universities to distance learning are presented. This study demonstrated the necessity of implementing a culture of online teaching in the Ukrainian higher education system, increasing sensitivity to student needs, and developing information and communication competence as a critical component of faculty professional self-realization.

In turn, the full-scale invasion that exacerbated the Russian–Ukrainian war in February 2022 raised the requirements for a culturally sensitive approach in Ukrainian higher education to a new level. Internally displaced persons (IDPs) and refugees from eastern Ukraine, Ukrainians who went abroad (but continue to study and teach in Ukrainian universities), or those who remained in occupied territories and later returned (or will eventually return) to the Ukrainian educational space—all these participants in the educational process have experienced cross-cultural shock and require psychological support and the cultivation of a caring, empathetic, inclusive, yet leadership-driven and motivating educational environment. A culturally sensitive approach to coaching aims to create an environment (space) that considers the specifics of local traditions, views, conditions, and needs, offering more individualized and effective coaching programs for educators.

These coaching programs must be modern and competitive, utilize the latest technologies and innovative teaching methods, be adapted to modernizing and improving the quality of Ukrainian higher education, and be suitable for rapid mastery by faculty members of Ukrainian universities. Koopman et al. (2021) analyzed the global history and stages of coaching as a discipline and the cultural, social, and economic factors that influenced its development. According to the researchers, the main trends and challenges faced by coaching as a discipline today are linked to globalization and the acceleration of technological progress. Passmore et al. (2024) believe that these global processes necessitate innovative online technologies and the

technical capabilities of artificial intelligence in implementing coaching programs in higher education practice. In the Ukrainian context, this could not only ensure the effective adaptation of coaching programs to the specific societal challenges of the Russian–Ukrainian war but also create prerequisites for sociopsychological support for students, high-quality educational management, and the professional self-realization of Ukrainian university faculty in the future.

The proposed concept of integrating coaching as an essential component of the development and professional self-realization of university faculty in Ukraine and improving the quality of higher education has demonstrated its relevance and pointed the way for systemic and structural changes in the educational process. These changes should involve all participants in the educational space: faculty, students, and university administration, addressing their current personal, sociocultural, and professional needs. Such an inclusive, caring, empathetic, and motivating educational environment will ensure professional growth and a continuous exchange of knowledge and experience among university faculty through mutual coaching, self-coaching, and mentoring. In creating such an educational coaching space, it is important to refer to the research by Lofthouse (2018), who studied the impact of coaching programs on the professional development of educators. The results of this study demonstrated the positive impact of coaching on improving teaching effectiveness, increasing motivation, and enhancing well-being and job satisfaction. It was also found that coaching helps faculty develop professional competencies and better understand their strengths and weaknesses to identify areas for further improvement. However, the need for more detailed research and development remains, particularly regarding the systematic implementation of coaching programs in Ukrainian universities during and after wartime.

Since coaching is closely linked to the concept of leadership, the development of leadership skills was also included in the coaching support model for university faculty. To fully develop their leadership qualities, university faculty members must cultivate skills in effective communication, team management, conflict resolution, and strategic planning competencies that enhance professional effectiveness and positively impact the self-realization of colleagues and students. Given these aspects, coaching becomes an essential tool for developing leadership potential, improving the quality of education, and creating a conducive learning environment in universities. Reid et al. (2020) studied the relationship between teaching and coaching in the context of management effectiveness. The authors explored how coaching can improve management functions and leadership skills in the educational field. Coaching helps educators develop strategic thinking, leadership qualities, and personnel management skills. Implementing coaching programs also promotes better communication skills and conflict-resolution abilities. It stimulates the professional self-development of education managers, which aligns with the positive effects of coaching practices identified in this study.

Enhancing and reinforcing social motivation through coaching is a significant strategy for fostering overall motivation for personal development and professional self-realization among university faculty. Through coaching, faculty members have the opportunity to feel supported and appreciated by colleagues, students, and the administration, which boosts their confidence and encourages further self-development. The study by Keiler et al. (2020) examined the impact of feedback on mentoring faculty and how coaches, colleagues, and students influence positive changes in them. The results showed that effective feedback is crucial for mentoring among faculty. Coaches, colleagues, and students are essential in providing constructive criticism, psychological support, and feedback that helps university faculty make changes and improve their teaching practices. Thus, social motivation catalyzes achieving high results in professional activities and creates a favorable psychological climate in higher education institutions. The various aspects of coaching highlighted in the reviewed works and the

researchers' conclusions have demonstrated the positive effects of using a wide range of coaching approaches, methods, and technologies. It has been established that coaching positively impacts the personal and professional qualities of faculty, helps develop leadership skills, and fosters effective communication with students, ultimately supporting the professional self-realization of university faculty. This underscores the strong need to develop a coaching culture, implement coaching philosophy and methods in the Ukrainian higher education system, and support these processes at the state level.

Positive psychology, which emphasizes the positive elements of human experience, has significantly impacted coaching practice (2016). Strength-based coaching, for instance, aims to pinpoint and capitalize on a person's abilities and skills to improve their performance and general efficacy as a leader or executive. In this vein, possibilities and peculiarities of integrating coaching into talent management seem to be highly expedient vectors of further studies, especially in wartime Ukraine, which is experiencing a deficit of pedagogical staff due to army recruitment and being under the challenge of the necessity to reorganize the higher education landscape in conditions of war impact. Furthermore, what results from coaching may influence must be addressed on several levels, like many treatments meant to enhance workplace performance. Kotte and Bozer (2022) explained using a four-level model based on Kirkpatrick's hierarchy, drawing on the literature on training efficacy. Subjectively perceived benefit, emotional and cognitive learning outcomes, client behavior change, and performance outcomes are the levels in this paradigm. Similarly, Jones et al. (2016) used a training-based view of outcomes. According to this approach, predicted outcomes may be divided into three groups: skill-based, cognitive, and emotive. The study has two limitations: the small size of the sample and the fact that it covers only one country. Further studies are needed to deepen the potential and challenges of coaching within HEIs' organizational environment, including in common plane and country-specific perspectives, based on a broader sample and considering diversity (gender, etc.).

4. Conclusion

The research examined the most common coaching approaches, areas of coaching application in higher education, and the coaching needs of university educators in Ukraine. This allowed for the development of a coaching support model for university faculty. The proposed model was based on the need for harmonious integration of coaching into the professional lives of educators and aimed at expanding their professional competencies and developing personal qualities. The motivational factors for self-development among university faculty indicated that the stimulus for their professional self-realization could stem from a variety of factors, including personal interests (e.g., the desire to enhance professional competence), material and non-material incentives, social support, the pursuit of knowledge and learning, the desire to have control over their professional development and decision-making, positive emotions and feelings experienced in the course of work, and many others. The study showed that coaching could help educators find meaning in their professional activities, significantly enhance existing motivation, identify internal sources of inspiration, and determine personal goals and values.

Emotional intelligence, reflection, and self-awareness are essential factors that contribute to successful self-development and professional self-realization for educators in higher education. They help them better understand and manage emotions, interact with others, maintain motivation, and collaborate effectively in an academic environment. Coaching focused on developing all these psychological components could significantly enhance educators' professional competence and personal fulfillment. The study also identified factors that promote professional self-realization for educators, including coaching and mentoring, related

activities (e.g., professional development and participation in professional associations and networks), and personal and social factors (motivation, social support, self-development). Based on the examined factors and psychological aspects of self-development and professional self-realization, coaching types and directions relevant to educators working in Ukraine's higher education system were proposed. Figure 4 describes a potential model for introducing a coaching approach to academic leadership within an HEI.

Figure 4. Coach Culture Cycle. Adapted from Callaghan (2022)

The above cycle, suggested by Callaghan, well suits the change model ADKAR (awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement) –the only reliable model for changes in social systems under unstable conditions, which is the case for Ukraine. Shaping awareness of the need for change and the desire to support the change seems to be the first step in introducing coaching into the practice, organizational culture, and organizational behavior of Ukrainian HEIs. Integrating the coaching approach into existing talent management systems and career progression could become a good start in implementing the coaching framework. The limitation of this study, in addition to the above-mentioned ones, was the insufficient empirical data on the self-development and professional self-realization of university faculty in Ukraine under the full-scale Russo-Ukrainian war. Therefore, it is recommended that future research explore the impact of traumatic events during societal crises (such as the global COVID-19 pandemic and war) on Ukrainian education sector workers, which could eventually allow for the adjustment of the proposed coaching approaches and models in Ukraine's higher education system.

Ethical Issues

Regarding the ethical considerations of the research, an informed consent letter was distributed to all participants before their involvement. The consent form was formulated to

give participants adequate information about the study, help them understand the research aims, and ensure voluntary participation. Matters concerning anonymity and confidentiality were also addressed and explained to the participants.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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